

THE MOST RELEVANT FACTORS AND METHODS OF INDEPENDENT STUDY OF HIGHER MATHEMATICS

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Annotasiya: Ilmiy va ishlab chiqarish sohalarida oliy matematikaning ko'plab qo'llanilishlarini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Ilmiy izlanishda bo'lgan yoki tadqiqot olib borayotgan vaqtda matematik bilimga duch keladi va oliy matematikani o'rganish zaruriyati tug'iladi. Oliy matematikani mustaqil o'rganish bo'yicha muxim omillar keltirilgan.

Аннотация: Мы видим множество применений высшей математики в научных и промышленных областях. Проводя научные исследования или проводя исследования, он сталкивается с математическими знаниями и возникает необходимость изучения высшей математики. Приведены важные факторы для самостоятельного изучения высшей математики.

Annotation: We see many applications of higher mathematics in scientific and industrial fields. While carrying out scientific research or carrying out research, he comes across mathematical knowledge and the need arises to study higher mathematics. Important factors for independent study of higher mathematics are given.

Kalit so'zlar: dasturiy ta'minot, ko'nikma, texnologiya, tadqiqot, usul, soha, internet, bilim.

Ключевые слова: программное обеспечение, навыки, технологии, исследования, метод, отрасль, интернет, знания.

Keywords: software, skills, technology, research, method, field, internet, knowledge.

An independent researcher or a specialist in the field in which the need arises to study some section of higher mathematics (for example, a software engineer, a specialist in the field of Economics, engineers-mechanics, let us briefly suggest that researchers) will face several difficulties in the process of independent study of higher mathematics.

Let's give an idea of how researchers can study higher mathematics. We think that this is considered one of the most important factors not only for researchers, but also for students.

A few years ago, a specialist who graduated from a higher educational institution and holds a master's degree, is engaged in work activities in any field.

It is not difficult to understand that skills in mathematics will decline over the years, perhaps this is the reason why there is no need to apply mathematics.

It is studied by reading scientific articles with the aim of studying new technologies within the next years. When trying to understand an article, mathematical symbols or methodology are often encountered that are unfamiliar. This can be attributed to the fact that the previous acquired mathematical knowledge was lost in memory, as well as faced with new methodologies. An attempt is made to look at what the article needs to be understood, but it makes it seem endless: it is necessary to know it before you understand it. Sometimes you find it impossible and it doesn't work.

People see mathematics as the best way to learn as updating what was taught in school many years ago.

Researchers, knowing what they learn from mathematics, buy books and notes and try to master them independently. The most frustrating thing, however, is the lack of rigor (which was very harsh during school periods), so when you have to try to understand the material in depth, you just have a peek. In general, everything seems to be correct, and only a partial understanding is formed.

The researcher will have to focus on following a method that ultimately matches the listener's level of math skills. That is, most mathematicians do not specialize in all areas of mathematics, so it can be more useful if you choose a specific small area and decide to specialize in it.

Taking these into account, Holda can be useful if we cite general tips. Learning mathematics is a long process. It will be necessary to act seriously, learn as much as possible and build a solid foundation of knowledge. It is necessary to select only the relevant areas (for example, optimization), study them and ignore others. Otherwise, too many gaps can be encountered, then the studies will be forgotten and returned again and again to that old material without any new understanding. Time is the investment needed to succeed in learning mathematics.

The deeper into pure mathematics, the better the elementary concepts of other mathematical tools used by scientists are understood. When mastering theoretical knowledge, it is often not difficult to remember what is actually happening.

The researcher has two main resources for independent study:

1. The researcher needs good books and should be given serious time to study them. When mastering certain knowledge from books, achieving mathematical maturity, it becomes necessary to gradually become an active master of mathematical knowledge.

2. Online resources are also very important. It is necessary to use the internet to ask questions and find lecture texts. The researcher will have to draw up his questions of interest, independently prove the theorems presented in the textbooks, or use mathematical blogs to study his ideas. In the process, it will be necessary to use the internet.

So: to achieve knowledge and maturity, it is necessary to use the internet to read good books, and at the same time to search for lecture texts, tables and videos that give less formal and intuitive explanations.

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